

Evolving T-Cells to Outsmart Cancer

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Abstract

Are modern treatments enough? There are treatments such as radiation therapy and chemotherapy, however, they cannot fully treat the ailment. Nevertheless, there are limitations with those cancer treatments because they target all cells and are not specific, have severe side effects, and have limited persistence. The promising nature of immunotherapy, especially for blood cancers, could have the same effect on solid tumors if refined and enhanced. Therefore, this concept of adaptive T-cell evolution would solve the obstacle of tumor immune evasion by allowing T-cells to evolve in real time, similar to how bacteria adapt under selective pressure. Self-editing T-cells would continuously reinforce their receptors and functions to counteract emerging tumor mutations and improve their effectiveness and longevity. This approach could create a universal and reliable approach to cancer treatment and more adequate personalized therapies. Moreover, this could usher in a new path of fully curing cancer as a whole. In a study by Dimitri et al., CRISPR-Cas9 technology has led to a surge in applying genome editing approaches to combat genetic disorders and cancers. The technology can induce specific mutations in the setting of in vitro and in vivo experimental disease models to study various interventional strategies. (Dimitri et al., 2022) This concept can be promising and change the trajectory of cancer treatment to be improved.

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Cancer is an inflammatory disease and is a constant challenge for many people regardless of age, ethnicity, country of origin, or lifestyle. Immune cells already help to rid the body of potential threats. For instance, immune cells help to break down ink particles in tattoos over time. This same function of immune cells is utilized against cancerous cells. Unfortunately, there is no sure way of avoiding cancer as it is prevalent, and there is a dire need for better

treatments. Cancer consistently evades immune responses, and current therapies such as CAR-T cell therapy (Engineered cancer-killing T-cells), checkpoint inhibitors (Immune system activation boosters), monoclonal antibodies (Identical lab-made immune proteins), and immunotherapy (a treatment approach that enhances the immune system's ability to fight cancer) has had no avail to treat it. Cancer treatments such as radiation therapy and chemotherapy have low success and are restricted due to their limited persistence, antigen loss, high toxicity, and non-specific targeting. These treatments would require further advances until they could cure the disease.

Contrarily, immunotherapy has shown success in recent trials, particularly for blood cancers. In a study by *J Immunol*, T cell-based immunotherapy demonstrated potential for treating cancer and various immune disorders. The application of methods for direct manipulation of genes is an adequate tool to define T cell subset functions, support the development of assays for screening, validate T cell targeting treatments, or improve immunotherapy. (*J Immunol*, 2018) Scientists have discovered that immunotherapy can advance to treat ailments like acute leukemias. CAR T-cell therapy also has an impact on the treatment of acute leukemias. "Pre-clinical data and clinical trials have shown promising results for immunotherapies in acute leukemia." (Chergui & Reagan, 2023) It is useful but it is restricted; however, it could be possible to augment these types of gene editing to function on solid tumors.

Further, bacteria can evolve and it is even observed in petri dishes. In fact, the process of Darwinian evolution explains the evolution of bacteria. Generally, bacteria evolve due to their rapid reproduction and the large number of individuals in a single colony. (Beckerson, 2024) T-cells could potentially use similar evolutionary strategies if engineered with gene-editing tools. The gene tools involving CRISPR/Cas9 (Precision DNA editing tool), Epigenetic Switches (gene expression control mechanism), and Hypermutation Zones (rapid mutation response areas)

would allow T-cells to autonomously control their functions, evolution, reproduction, response time, potency, and genetic editing. It would cause T-cells to adapt to various tumor mutations to become better over time in combating cancer. From these gene-editing tools, T-cells could be programmed to undergo controlled genetic modifications for improved recognition and neutralization of emerging tumor variants and simultaneously prevent harmful mutations.

Based on the gene-editing tools, enhanced immunotherapy would improve T-cell function. It would cause them to resolve the problem of tumor resistance and evasion. The concept of Adaptive T-cell evolution would be built upon the existing abilities of immune cells and amplified with better immunotherapy and gene-editing tools. T-cells would have built-in mechanisms to self-edit their DNA/RNA in response to cancer mutations similar to bacterial evolution. Through natural selection and reproduction, immune cells like T-cells can evolve to recognize and destroy abnormal cells. Theoretically, it would be possible to utilize the mechanisms bacteria and viruses used to grow rapidly and implant them into human immune cells via gene editing. One could implement protective matrices from bacteria into T-cells, causing them to adapt to new tumor mutations.

CRISPR-Cas9 is a tool for precise gene editing. It creates a surge in applying genome editing approaches to combat cancers, and, in these cases, inherited genetic diseases with known gene mutations can be corrected. (Dimitri et al., 2022) The technology is being explored to improve T-cell effector function and persistence, reduce treatment-related toxicity, and increase patient product availability. In other words, it is used to reduce the risks found in other conventional treatments like chemo, radiation therapy, and CAR-T therapy and to make it a superior option to cancer treatment. T-cells could potentially be programmed to self-edit and evolve in response to tumor mutations.

Discussion

Some long-term risks and challenges raise questions as to whether cancer treatments are ethical or not. For instance, with a similar concept of CAR-T cell therapy, there is a chance of chronic toxicities. “In a recent clinical study, Engineered cells persisted at high levels for 6 months in the blood and bone marrow and continued to express the chimeric antigen receptor. A specific immune response was detected in the bone marrow, accompanied by loss of normal B cells and leukemia cells that express CD19. Remission was ongoing 10 months after treatment. Hypogammaglobulinemia was an expected chronic toxic effect.” (Porter et al., 2011) Another common challenge in existing cancer treatments, such as gene editing, is that there are concerns about off-target effects leading to accidental gene disruption. “Preclinical development requires study and mitigation of off-target risks for any genome editing treatment before testing in humans.”(Christopher et al., 2019) However, safety protocols and post-treatment monitoring can mitigate these potential dangers. Standard practice for these medical applications could include tools like off-target prediction algorithms, Cas9 mutant, and Empiric methods to reduce the rate of off-target cleavage compared to wild-type enzymes. Even future advancements in Artificial Intelligence have the capacity to enhance precision and cancer treatment as a whole.

Conclusion

CRISPR-enhanced adaptive T-cells introduce real-time evolutionary flexibility, which is unmatched in current therapies; thus, it will be a refined version of existing treatments and will potentially be universal and enable immune cells to persist more in vitro. T-cells would be able to match the level of complexity and growth of cancerous cells. Over time, people could conduct trials and examinations on this theory as a universal cancer treatment strategy, as it is focused on developing ways to enhance the ability of the natural immune system to recognize and eliminate

tumor cells. With this concept, T-cells could target both blood and solid tumors while resisting antigen loss and tumor immune evasion, something that other treatments like CAR-T have shown to some extent. It is ideal that this concept of adaptive self-editing T-cells offers a solution to challenges regarding cancer treatment and could facilitate the production of a coherent cancer treatment. Empirical evidence is necessary before this concept becomes a reality. However, if invested, this concept could transform cancer from a fatal diagnosis into a curable disease.

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